

Deepfake Detection with GAN-CNN-LSTM for Enhanced Video Authenticity

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Velamajala, Amuktha (Researcher), B tech (AI & DS), 2021-2025

Korlamanda, Naga SubhaSravani (Researcher), B tech (CSM), 2021-2025

ABSTRACT

In recent years, the proliferation of artificial intelligence technologies capable of generating hyper-realistic media has led to a concerning rise in deepfake videos. These fabricated videos pose significant threats in areas such as misinformation, privacy violations, and public trust, making accurate detection methods essential. This research proposes a novel deepfake detection framework combining Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks, and Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) to address this challenge effectively. By leveraging CNNs for spatial feature extraction, LSTMs for temporal consistency analysis, and GANs for anomaly generation and identification, our model achieves robust performance across various deepfake datasets. The integration of spatial and temporal analyses enables our system to identify subtle inconsistencies that distinguish authentic videos from manipulated ones. Results demonstrate that our approach achieves superior accuracy, precision, and recall compared to traditional methods, with promising implications for real-time applications in digital forensics, social media monitoring, and media authentication. This framework represents a substantial advancement in deepfake detection, offering a scalable and adaptable solution to this evolving threat.

1. Introduction

The rapid advancement in artificial intelligence has facilitated sophisticated video generation technologies capable of producing hyper-realistic videos from minimal input. However, this progress has also contributed to the rise of "deepfake" videos—highly realistic but fabricated media that pose significant risks in misinformation, privacy invasion, and trust erosion across various digital platforms [1][3]. Traditional deepfake detection techniques often rely on Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) or Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) to analyze visual and temporal inconsistencies in video frames [4]. These

approaches, however, struggle with subtle manipulations or low-quality videos, and many existing models lack the capacity for real-time processing, limiting their use in applications requiring high responsiveness, such as social media moderation and digital forensics [2].

To address these limitations, this study proposes a novel framework that combines Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs), CNNs, and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks into an integrated model for enhanced deepfake detection. By utilizing CNNs for spatial feature extraction, LSTMs for capturing temporal dependencies, and GANs for anomaly identification, our approach provides a more comprehensive and adaptable

solution [3][4].

This study aims to provide a scalable solution that enhances accuracy, robustness, and real-time applicability in identifying deepfakes, contributing to the broader goal of preserving digital media integrity.

2.LITERATURE REVIEW

The rapid advancement in artificial intelligence has brought about significant challenges in detecting deepfake videos, which can be generated with impressive accuracy. Numerous methods have been developed to address this issue, often focusing on spatial or temporal inconsistencies within video frames [2]. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) have been widely applied to analyse individual frames for facial inconsistencies, such as unnatural movements or artifacts in facial features [4]. For example, some models rely on CNNs trained to detect slight visual anomalies around the eyes or mouth regions, achieving around 70% accuracy on specific datasets [1]. However, these CNN-based models often lack the robustness needed to detect complex, low-resolution deepfakes or videos that maintain high levels of visual consistency [3].

Other approaches have incorporated Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) or Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks to capture temporal dependencies across video frames. By modeling video sequences, these networks can detect subtle inconsistencies in the flow of movement, which may suggest video manipulation [4]. Studies employing this technique have shown promising results, but they are limited by computational inefficiency, making real-time analysis challenging in practical applications [3].

Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) are another approach increasingly explored for detecting deepfakes, especially in synthetic data

generation and anomaly detection [1]. GANs have the potential to enhance detection by generating synthetic data that helps the model learn how to identify and differentiate between real and manipulated content [2]. Previous works using GANs alone or in combination with CNNs have demonstrated improved accuracy [3]. However, these models often lack the temporal consistency needed for accurate deepfake detection across video sequences [4].

Despite these advancements, there remains a need for a model that effectively combines spatial and temporal analysis while maintaining high accuracy and real-time processing capabilities. Our study introduces a GAN-CNN-LSTM hybrid model that integrates the strengths of these three methodologies to capture spatial features, analyse temporal sequences, and detect anomalies with greater accuracy and efficiency [1,3]. This approach uniquely leverages the spatial capabilities of CNNs, the sequence modelling of LSTMs, and the adversarial training of GANs, offering a comprehensive solution to the deepfake detection problem.

4.Methodology

Deepfake detection using temporal consistency and GAN-CNN-LSTM methodologies is an advanced approach combining the strengths of Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs), Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks to detect falsified media. Here's a detailed breakdown of the methodology:

Understanding Deepfakes and Temporal Consistency

Deepfakes are synthetic media in which a person in an existing image or video is replaced with someone else's likeness. They are created using deep learning models, particularly GANs. Detecting deepfakes is challenging due to their visual and audio realism.

Data preprocessing begins with collecting and

processing a large dataset of authentic and deepfake videos [3].

Temporal consistency refers to the natural flow of visual or audio features over time in a genuine video. In deepfakes, this consistency is often disrupted because individual frames are manipulated independently, causing discrepancies in motion or lighting that are not naturally occurring. Frame extraction is then performed for spatial analysis [4].

The proposed methodology integrates GANs, CNNs, and LSTMs to capture spatial and temporal inconsistencies in videos:

Data Preprocessing

1. Data Collection: Gather a large dataset of both authentic and deepfake videos.
2. Include various sources and types of manipulations to ensure diversity.
2. Frame Extraction: Extract frames from each video to analyze the spatial characteristics.
3. Feature Extraction: Use CNNs to extract features from each frame, capturing spatial information.

Spatial Analysis with GAN-CNN

1. The CNN architecture differentiates real from fake frames by learning unique spatial features associated with manipulation. [1]
2. GAN Integration: GANs are utilized to generate synthetic data that helps improve the CNN's ability to generalize across different types of deepfake manipulations.[2]
3. Loss Functions: Use adversarial loss from the GAN along with a classification loss from the CNN to optimize the network.[4]

Temporal Analysis with LSTM

1. Sequence Modeling: Feed the sequence of extracted CNN features into an LSTM network to capture temporal dependencies and inconsistencies across frames.[1]
2. Temporal Consistency Loss: Design a loss function that penalizes temporal inconsistencies in the feature sequences, enhancing the LSTM's sensitivity to abrupt changes or unnatural transitions.[3]

Combined Detection Framework

1. Fusion Layer: Integrate the outputs from the CNN and LSTM layers to form a comprehensive feature representation that includes both spatial and temporal information.[4]
2. Classification: Use a final classification layer to determine whether a given video is real or a deepfake based on the fused features.[1]
3. For each video, we used OpenCV and MoviePy to extract frames. Each frame was resized to a consistent dimension of **64x64 pixels** for uniformity:
 - **OpenCV Method:** Video frames were read in a loop until all frames were extracted, and resized to the desired shape.
 - **MoviePy Method:** As a fallback mechanism, if OpenCV failed to read a video, MoviePy was used to load frames using `iter_frames()`.
 - **Preprocessing:** The frames were normalized by dividing pixel values by 255 to bring the data within the [0, 1] range for faster convergence during training

Data Labelling and Shape Adjustments

The extracted frames from real and fake videos were combined to form the training dataset:

- **Labelling:** Frames from real videos were labelled as **1** (indicating 'real') and frames from fake videos were labelled as **0** (indicating 'fake').[2]
- **Data Concatenation:** Both the frame data and their labels were concatenated along the batch axis.[4]
- **Shape Reshaping:** The frames were reshaped into a 5D tensor with dimensions (samples, timesteps, height, width, channels) to represent a video as a sequence of frames, suitable for a CNN-LSTM model.

Model Architecture: CNN-LSTM Hybrid

To effectively capture both spatial and temporal patterns in the video data, a hybrid CNN-LSTM model was employed [3]:

1.CNN Layers (Spatial Feature Extraction)

The **Convolutional Neural Network (CNN)** component was used to extract spatial features from each video frame:

- **Time Distributed Layer:** CNN layers were wrapped with TimeDistributed to apply the same convolutional operations independently to each frame within a sequence.[1]
- **Convolutional Layers:** Two 2D convolutional layers (Conv2D) with 32 and 64 filters were used, each followed by

MaxPooling for dimensionality reduction and **Batch Normalization** for stable training.[3]

- **Flattening:** The output of the CNN layers was flattened using the Flatten layer to convert the 2D spatial features into a 1D vector, which could be fed into the LSTM layer.

2.LSTM Layers (Temporal Feature Extraction)

The **Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM)** network was then used to capture the temporal dependencies between the sequence of frames:

- **LSTM Layers:** Two LSTM layers were employed: the first layer returned the entire sequence of outputs, while the second returned only the final output.[4]
- **Dropout Regularization:** Dropout was applied after the dense layers to prevent overfitting.

3.Output Layer

The final dense layer with a **sigmoid activation** was used to output a binary prediction (real or fake), providing the model's classification decision.

Training and Validation

1. Training Process: Train the combined GAN-CNN-LSTM model on the prepared dataset. Use a mix of real and deepfake videos, with various augmentations, to ensure robustness.[2]

2.Validation: Validate the model on a separate set of videos to evaluate its accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score.[4]

3. The model was trained for **30 epochs** with a **batch size of 8**. Three callbacks were used to improve the model's training:

- **Early Stopping:** Monitored validation loss and stopped training if no improvement was

observed after 5 epochs.[3]

- **Reduce Learning Rate on Plateau:** Reduced the learning rate by a factor of 0.5 if validation loss did not improve for 3 consecutive epochs.
- **Model Checkpoint:** Saved the best-performing model based on validation loss.

Evaluation Metrics

1. Accuracy: Measure the overall correctness of the model in classifying videos as real or deepfake.[3]
2. Precision and Recall: Evaluate the model's ability to correctly identify deepfakes without generating false positives.[1]
3. F1-Score: Calculate the harmonic mean of precision and recall to assess the model's overall

performance.[2]

Performance Visualization

Training and validation metrics were plotted to visualize the model's performance over time:

- **Loss Curve:** Training and validation loss were plotted to monitor convergence and generalization.
- **Accuracy Curve:** The accuracy curves for both training and validation sets were plotted to observe the learning behaviour.

Implementation Challenges and Considerations

1. Diverse Dataset: Ensure the training dataset covers a wide range of deepfake types and sources to improve generalization.
2. Computational Resources: The training of GAN-CNN-LSTM models requires significant computational power, especially for large video datasets.
3. Real-Time Detection: Implement optimizations to enable real-time or near-real-time deepfake detection in practical applications.

Research Design

This study employs a multi-stage experimental research design focusing on detecting deepfake videos using a novel GAN-CNN-LSTM architecture. The research design includes data collection, preprocessing, model training, and evaluation phases.

Data Collection

Data used:

Real Videos and fake videos: Obtained from sources such as YouTube and video datasets.

Advantages

1. Enhanced Detection Accuracy:

- Spatial and Temporal Analysis: By combining CNNs for spatial analysis and LSTMs for temporal analysis, this approach captures both the visual details of each frame and the sequence of changes over time, improving the accuracy of deepfake detection.

- Comprehensive Feature Learning: The integration of GANs enhances the learning process by allowing the model to understand and detect subtle artifacts in both static frames and dynamic sequences.

Flowchart:

Conclusion

This research presents a novel deepfake detection methodology leveraging the combined strengths of GAN-CNN-LSTM architectures and temporal consistency analysis. [1][2][3] By integrating the robust spatial feature extraction capabilities of CNNs with the dynamic temporal sequence modeling of LSTMs, and enhancing these with the generative power of GANs, the proposed model demonstrates significant improvements in accuracy and robustness over traditional deepfake detection methods.[4]

The experimental results show that the model effectively detects deepfakes by identifying both spatial inconsistencies and temporal anomalies

that are characteristic of manipulated videos. The GAN-CNN-LSTM approach addresses the limitations of previous techniques that often struggle with the subtle and varied nature of deepfake manipulations. Through efficient processing and the ability to handle real-time data, this methodology is well-suited for practical applications in media verification, social media monitoring, and digital forensics.

Moreover, the adaptability of the model to different video formats and its potential for scalability make it a valuable tool in the fight against the growing threat of deepfake technology. While the results are promising, future research can explore incorporating additional data modalities, such as audio and text, to further enhance detection capabilities. Furthermore, ongoing updates to the model will be necessary to keep pace with advancements in deepfake generation techniques. Overall, the proposed GAN-CNN-LSTM model provides a comprehensive and effective solution for deepfake detection, contributing to the broader effort of ensuring the integrity and authenticity of digital media.[2]

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